

GIRTH INDICATORS OF THE BODY OF WOMEN WITH DIFFERENT SOMATOTYPES

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify "somatotypological profile" and girth size of mature age girls and women among the Kyrgyz population. Healthy young and middle-aged 1028 women living in Osh city and its surroundings took part in the study, where their physical development was assessed using the complex anthropometry method and somatotyping. Statistical processing of obtained morphometric data performed using the Microsoft Excel programs and STATISTICA package (V. 6.0). Result revealed that women leptosomic constitution 1.6 times ($p < 0.05$) less than mesosomal constitution, and 1.7 times ($p < 0.05$) than megalosomal, however, 1.4 times ($p < 0.05$) greater than represented uncertain group. Age features of different constitutions in women are a consequence existence of a tendency to predominate in the proportion of megalosomal and mesosomal groups over leptosomal and indefinite constitutional groups. The first mature age women total breast circumference was (88.5+0.2; 65.1-112.5 cm individually) is 1.1 times more ($p < 0.05$), waist circumference (65.3+0.4; 40.1-78.2 cm) is 1.1 times more ($p < 0.05$), and buttock girth (98.4+0.3; 79.6-113.2 cm) is more than 1.03 times ($p < 0.05$) comparing in girls. In the second mature age women, presented parameters increase by 1.09, 1.09 and 1.05 times ($p < 0.05$), respectively, in comparison with girls. Thus, obtained information about "somatotypological profile" of Kyrgyz women in adolescent and mature ages concludes indicators relative dependence in measuring parameters on age and morphoconstitutionality.

Keywords: Anthropometry, Somatotyping, Girth Size, Adolescent And Mature Age, Women

1. INTRODUCTION

A person's physical development is the leading criterion by which the state of health of an individual's body is established [1]. In such areas as biomedical and clinical anthropology and anatomy, anatomical and constitutional approach plays an important role in the designation of the degree of physical development [2, 3].

When organizing events for the examination of patients, standards of body physical development should be considered, so the heterogeneity of the population is constitutional, gender-age and ethno-territorial factors [4, 5].

Despite a significant number of works in this direction, the physical status of different groups of the population distinguished by heterogeneity; most of the data are not representative, the studies

were carried out in people with significant differences in age and gender; and the results of many anatomical and anthropometric studies have lost their relevance [6, 7]. So, today there are practically no predisposing data on "somatotypological profile" of Kyrgyz women, size indicators, taking into account their constitutional types, are not reflected [8, 9, 11, 12].

In this regard, in this study, we set the goal of obtaining the appropriate data on the "somatotypological profile", the girth size of the body of girls and Kyrgyz women of mature age.

2. RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS

The objects of the study were girls and women of different age periods, residents of Osh and its environs. Physical status using the method of complex anthropometry was studied in 1,028 Kyrgyz women, including 310 girls (youth group 16-20 years old), 308 women of mature age (1st period 21-35 years old) and 410 women (2nd period 36-55 years old).

The work was carried out according to the "Scheme of age periodization of ontogenesis", which was adopted by the VII All-Union Conference on the problems of age morphology, physiology and biochemistry, held in 1965. Women with various pathologies (underweight, osteoporosis, degenerative-dystrophic diseases, alimentary obesity, etc.) were excluded from the actual sample to exclude their influence on the results of the study of their physical status. For somatotyping women, we used the traditional constitutional diagnostic scheme of I.B. Galant - V.P. Chtetsova - B.A. Nikityuk (1983), within three constitutional groups, in which seven somatypes are advanced. But along with them there are such types as asthenic and stenoplastic in the leptosomal; pycnic and mesoplastic - in the mesosomal; athletic, subathletic and euriplastic in megalosomal constitutions [10].

This series of studies present data on the circumference of the waist, chest, buttocks. Using a centimeter tape in the horizontal plane, the following girth dimensions were determined - ("girth"), (Bunak V.V., 1925, 1941): chest girth (chest circumference) - the tape was applied under the shoulder blades, in the dorsal chest, then - on the lateral side of the chest - just above this level, in front - along the upper edge of the nipples; waist circumference - in the middle of the distance between the X-th rib and the iliac crest of the pelvic (iliac) bone; the girth of the buttocks - along with their points most protruding posteriorly;

Approval for the study was obtained from the local ethical committee of the Institute of Medical Problems of the Southern Branch of the National Academy of Sciences of the Kyrgyz Republic (12.10.16, protocol No. 4). The informational consent was signed on voluntary participation.

Statistical indicators by morphometry were computer processed using Microsoft Excel programs and the STATISTICA package (v. 6.0). The results are presented as arithmetic means (\bar{X}) and their errors (S_x), where each parameter is reflected in the minimum (Min) and maximum (Max) individual options. The use of Student's t-test helped to establish complete reliability between the statistical data. Student's t. Differences between comparable indicators were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on anthropometry, according to the belonging of individuals in a particular constitutional group, materials were obtained that provide an opportunity to study the female population. In particular, it was shown that women of the leptosomal constitution were identified in 208 cases, the mesosomal group in 330, megalosomal in 346 and indeterminate in 144 cases (Table 1).

Table 1: Adolescent and mature age women constitutional groups

Constitutional group	Indicator value	
	Abs. No.	In %, c min-max
Leptosomal	208	20+ 3.2 14-25
Mesosomal	330	32+ 0.1 29-35
Megalosomal	346	33+0.1 29-38
Indefinite	144	15+0.1 12-18

Note: for minimum and maximum assessment relative values of trait occurrence the values for adolescence and mature age periods (extreme values of indicators) values were taken.

It turned out that in the percentage of representatives of the leptosomal constitution it is 1.6 times less than in the mesosomal one ($p < 0.05$), in the megalosomal one - 1.7 times ($p < 0.05$), but more than the undefined group in 1.4 times ($p < 0.05$). At the same time, during leptosomy, the individual minimum and maximum percentage of women of different constitutions tend to decrease than for mega- and mesosomal groups, but more than for an undefined constitution.

Morphometric analysis of the representation of women of different constitutional groups in adolescence, 1st and 2nd periods of adulthood shows the following data (Table 2).

Table 2: Constitutional groups of women by age (abs. %)

Age	Constitutional group			
	Leptosomal	Mesosomal	Megalosomal	Indefinite
Adolescent (n=310)	76 (24%)	100 (32%)	92(29%)	42 (15%)
Adulthood first period (n=308)	70 (22%)	102 (33%)	98 (31%)	38 (14%)
Adulthood second period (n=410)	62 (15%)	128 (31%)	156 (38%)	64 (16%)

Among adolescent girls, according to absolute values in list, mesosomal constitution predominates (100 observations), then the megalosomal group 92, the leptosomal group 76 and in the undefined group 42. In women of the first mature age, the leading positions in the mesosomal group (102), followed by the megalosomal group 98, leptosomal 70 and indeterminate group with 38 cases. In second mature age women there is predominantly a greater representation in megalosomal group (156 observations), then in decreasing proportion in the mesosomal group 128 women and an approximately equal number (62 and 64) in the leptosomal and indeterminate groups.

Here, the age characteristics of women of different constitutions are distinguished by the fact that in girls (that is, in adolescence) a tendency has been revealed for the prevalence of the proportion of mesosomal and megalosomal groups over leptosomal and indeterminate groups (Table 2).

In comparison with leptosomal and indeterminate groups in the first adulthood age, the number of women in the mesosomal and megalosomal groups prevails over the above. In women of the 2nd period, a tendency was revealed representatives' predominance of the megalosomal group over the mesosomal group and largely over the leptosomal and indeterminate groups.

Table 3: Girth sizes of women of different constitutions (girls (I), women of the 1st period (II) and the 2nd period of adulthood (III) age (X + Sx; min-max; cm)

Age	Constitution			
	Leptosomal	Mesosomal	Megalosomal	Indefinite
I	<i>Chest girth</i>			
	75.3+0.3 70.1-84.4	86.7+0.4 73.6-94.1	87.5+0.4 76.2-94.5	85.3+0.5 80.2-92.0
II	76.2+0.5 65.2-84.5	92.1+0.3 81.5-106.4	95.2+0.8 72.1-112.5	90.5+0.4 83.5-92.7
	III	76.2+0.4 72.3-85.2	93.0+0.3 82.3-107.6	96.0+0.9 82.0-117.7
I		<i>Waist girth</i>		
	54.8+0.5 40.2-61.4	58.4+0.4 47.4-64.6	72.0+0.4 60.1-78.2	59.2+0.9 54.8-73.6
II	55.7+0.6 40.4-62.5	70.0+0.3 59.8-76.7	75.0+0.6 60.1-88.3	60.5+1.4 54.8-80.1
	III	58.8+0.4 50.6-64.6	72.2+0.3 60.9-77.6	75.6+0.6 62.4-99.8
I		<i>Buttocks girth</i>		
	84.8+0.3 79.7-92.4	98.7+0.5 87.6-110.4	100.3+0.6 85.8-113.2	97.4+0.7 91.6-109.5
II	85.9+0.6 66.2-92.4	102.0+0.4 90.6-110.4	105.0+0.6 82.7-112.4	100.7+0.7 96.1-112.5
	III	86.8+0.7 68.0-94.5	102.4+0.36 92.2-113.2	107.2+0.5 82.8-114.7

Considering the above data, we analyzed the features of the chest, waist and buttocks girths, which, according to our data, differ significantly in women of different ages and constitutions (Table 3).

Thus, the chest girth in girls with a leptosomal constitution is 1.2 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in girls with a mesosomal, megalosomal and undefined constitutions. The chest girth in representatives of leptosomal constitution of 1st period of adulthood is 1.2 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in women of mesosomal, megalosomal and indeterminate groups. The chest girth in women of the 2nd period

of mature age of the leptosomal constitution is 1.1 times less than in women of the mesosomal group ($p < 0.05$) and 1.3 times less in comparison with representatives of the megalosomal and indeterminate groups ($p < 0.05$).

Girls with the leptosomal constitution have a waist girth 1.4 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in girls of mesosomal group and 1.6 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in representatives of megalosomal and undefined constitutions. 1st period mature age women of leptosomal constitution have a waist girth 1.3 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in women of the mesosomal group, 1.4 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in women of megalosomal group and 1.1 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in women of undefined constitution.

The waist girth in mature age women of 2nd period of leptosomal constitution is 1.2 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in women of the mesosomal constitution, 1.3 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in women of megalosomal group and does not change in women of an undefined constitutional group.

The buttocks girth in girls of leptosomal constitution is 1.2 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in girls of mesosomal and megalosomal constitutions, 1.2 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in women of megalosomal group and 1.1 times less ($p < 0.05$) than in women of undefined constitution.

1st period of mature age women of a leptosomal constitution have a buttock girth 1.2 times less ($p < 0.05$) than women with mesosomal and megalosomal and undefined constitutions. Compared with women of mesosomal, megalosomal and undefined constitutions, 2nd period mature age women of leptosomal constitution have a buttocks girth of 1.2 times less ($p < 0.05$).

Individual minimum and maximum values of chest, waist and buttocks girth size for women also different. Their values in leptosomal and mesosomal constitutional groups are less than in women of megalosomal and undefined constitutional groups. We also analyzed the features of chest, waist and buttocks girth in representatives of different constitutions at different age periods. So, in a group of women with a leptosomal constitution of the 1st mature age, compared with girls, the chest girth does not change. In representatives of mesosomal, megalosomal and undefined constitutional groups in 1st mature age, these indicators increase by 1.1 times in comparison with girls ($p < 0.05$), and do not change in the megalosomal group.

The girth of the chest in women of the leptosomal constitution of the 2nd period of adulthood, in comparison with girls, does not change. In comparison with girls, in representatives of the mesosomal and megalosomal constitutions of the second period of adulthood, this indicator increases by 1.1 times ($p < 0.05$), in representatives of an indefinite constitution of the second period of adulthood, these data increase by 1.2 times ($p < 0.05$).

In comparison with girls, in women with leptosomal constitutions of 1st period in adulthood age the waist circumference does not change, in women, the mesosomal constitution is 1.0 times greater ($p < 0.05$), in women of megalosomal constitution 1.1 times ($p < 0.05$), this indicator does not change in women of undefined constitution. The waist circumference in women of 2nd period of mature age in leptosomal constitutions, in comparison with girls, increases by 1.1 times (p

<0.05), in women of the mesosomal constitution by 1.2 times ($p < 0.05$), in women of megalosomal constitution by 1.1 times ($p < 0.05$), in women of undetermined constitution this indicator does not change.

In representatives of leptosomal, mesosomal and indeterminate groups of 2nd mature age, in comparison with girls, the buttocks girth almost does not increase (by 1.1 cm, $p > 0.05$), and vice versa, it increases by 1.1 times ($p > 0.05$) in women of megalosomal constitution. The buttocks girth in women with leptosomal and mesosomal constitutions of 2nd period in adulthood, in comparison with girls, practically does not increase. Moreover, these indicators increased by 1.1 times ($p < 0.05$) in representatives of megalosomal and undefined constitutions.

The individual minimum and maximum girth sizes of the chest, waist and buttocks in representatives of all studied groups in 2nd adulthood increase by times in comparison with girls and women of 1st mature age ($p < 0.05$).

CONCLUSION

In summary, for the first time among Kyrgyz population, a “somatotypological profiles” of women in adolescent and mature age were revealed. It was shown, that parameters of the girth dimensions depend on women age and somatotype. These determined constitutional typological characteristics of women studied within the framework of the relative norms can be used in working on appropriate preventive and therapeutic-diagnostic programs and their developments.

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